

Nanostructure Controlled Bioplastics in the Design and Engineering of Sustainable Multifunctional Green Materials

A. K. Mohanty*^{1,2} and Rahul Bhardwaj³

¹Bioproducts Discovery and Development Centre, Department of Plant Agriculture, Crop Science Building, University of Guelph, Guelph, N1G-2W1, ON, Canada

²School of Engineering, Thornbrough Building, University of Guelph, Guelph, N1G-2W1, ON, Canada (* Correspondence author: mohanty@uoguelph.ca)

³PolyOne, Ohio, USA

SUMMARY

Bioplastics are of particular interest because of their renewability, biodegradability and environmental sustainability in reducing green house gas emission. There is a pressing need to enhance the versatility of the emerging bioplastics for more wide spread applications, and making them ready to compete with traditional non-biodegradable plastics. A transformative approach in creating a new range of smart biomaterials was initiated by incorporation of nanostructures into bioplastic, including revolutionary material combinations. Integrating the advantage of nanotechnology in bringing-out new sustainable biomaterials is considered as a strategic pathway towards innovation. A dendritic hyperbranched polymer (HBP) was tailored for inclusion into the bioplastic, which generated a nano-structure controlled bioplastic. A nano-structure controlled technology based on hyperbranched polymers improved the elongation at break, significantly with a very minimal sacrifice of the stiffness of polylactide. The reinforcements of these nano-structure controlled bioplastics with micro-/macro-/nano-fibers and particles alone or in combinations would help in the design and engineering a new class of multifunctional biomaterials. These multifunctional biomaterials can also be termed as hierarchical nano-biocomposites. A hierarchical, truly green nano-biocomposite is defined here as a natural fibre or nano-filler related composite of a nano-structure controlled bioplastics. The term “hierarchical” relates to the varying size order of reinforcements, from nano to macro. Varying material combinations are less complex than it may appear and are quite common in petroleum-based plastics and everyday materials. For example, a polypropylene plastic packaging we use may contain varying additives like antioxidants, stabilizers, pigments or colors and low-cost filler like talc.

INTRODUCTION

The consumer desire, environmental needs, government’s push for green products and national security are some of the major factors that drive research towards the development of renewable resource-based new materials. A biobased economy presents challenges to agriculture, forestry, academia, government and industry. The green polymers like polylactides, PLA; polyhydroxyalkanoates, PHAs; starch plastics; biobased poly (trimethylene terephthalate), and functionalized vegetable/plant oil-based resins are some examples of biologically derived materials that are moving rapidly towards mainstream applications¹⁻³. Two recently highlighted bioplastics (Scheme 1) are polylactides (PLA) and polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHAs). PHAs family of bioplastics include PHB and PHBV with varying valerate contents.

Poly lactides are the leading biodegradable polymers, which are looked upon as sustainable alternative to petroleum based plastics⁴. The primary interest in these polymers originated due to the production of their precursor, i.e. lactic acid, from renewable resources such as corn, sugar beet, sugarcane, cellulosic waste, and rice starch⁵⁻⁹. Currently NatureWorks LLC owned by Cargill is independently producing

Polyhydroxybutyrate-co-valerate (PHBV)

Polyhydroxybutyrate (PHB) Polylactide (PLA)

Scheme 1: Renewable Resource-based Bioplastics; PLA, PHB and PHBV

PLA from corn based feedstock in its plant at Blair, Nebraska, USA. NatureWorks, with a PLA production capacity of 140,000 t per annum, is the single largest producer of PLA bioplastic. Although currently, commercially available PLA possess high strength and stiffness, its inherently poor properties, such as poor impact strength, low elongation at break, poor melt strength, low heat deflection temperature (HDT), narrow processing window and low

thermal stability are impeding its large scale commercial applications in various uses. Therefore, modification of PLA properties is necessary for developing it as a commodity plastic. Several methods such as copolymerization, plasticization, blending, and clay based nanocomposites have been mentioned in the literature, to improve upon the toughness and flexibility of polylactides¹⁰. Other properties like heat deflection temperature, gas barrier and stiffness are improved by clay based nanocomposites.

Blending two different polymers in order to enhance properties is a challenging task. Conventional blending techniques have limitation of macroscopic phase separation between the two incompatible polymer constituents. This is due to the difference in their surface tension, lack of interface adhesion and improper domain size of the dispersed phase. Nanostructure blending is a newly emerging process to overcome the weaknesses of conventional blending. It refers to the fabrication of polymeric blends in which the dispersed phase dimensions are below 100 nm. In a customary blending, it is almost impossible to achieve the phase dimensions of this order. The most common approaches used to obtain nanostructure blends are reactive blending, block copolymerization and high shear processing. The nanostructure blending can create transparent, super tough materials with high thermo-mechanical properties.

NANOBLENDING AND NANOSTRUCTURE CONTROLLED BIOPLASTICS

Nano-structure controlled bioplastic or nano-blend of bioplastic is quite new to the scientific literature^{11,12}. Some of the key demerits that stymie the use of biopolymers are their brittleness, higher density, higher melt viscosity and lower heat deflection temperature (HDT), when compared to certain petroleum-based plastics. Biopolymers require property improvements to accomplish the balance between stiffness and toughness. The other essential improvements are reduced melt viscosity and higher melt strength. Conventional blending methods are limiting, in terms of macroscopic phase

separation between incompatible polymer partners, due to different surface tensions, lack of interfacial adhesion and improper domain size of the dispersed phase. We discovered nanostructure blending, which overcomes these limitations. The dispersed polymeric phase in the nanostructured system has domains below 100 nm. These dimensions are almost impossible to achieve in the conventional blending. Nanostructure blending combined with nanoscale filler (organo-clay, carbon nanotubes etc.) and/or micro/macro-type (talc/biofibre) reinforcements will provide a basis for the next generation of smart biomaterials.

Different types of polymers, when blended together can exhibit enhanced mechanical, optical and electro-optical properties, especially if the blend morphology is formed at submicrometer or nanometer scales. Fabrication and designing of thermodynamically stable polymer blends are having structures at submicrometer/nanometer scales poses significant scientific and industrial challenges. These nanostructured materials present a unique combination of properties, which are impossible to achieve with classical blends. Most of the polymer blends processed under typical extrusion conditions; the particle size of the dispersed phase is rarely below 0.1 μ (or 100 nm) irrespective of the compatibilization method employed. Polyethylene and polyamide have been melt blended to obtain new co-continuous morphologies at nanometer scale. The principle interest in the nanostructured polymer blends is because of the enhanced properties like:

- Improved transparency
- Superior toughness
- High heat resistance
- Remarkable creep resistance
- Superior stiffness-toughness balance
- Effective at low concentration of tough polymer
- Retain properties after annealing

Approaches to Prepare Nanostructure Blends

In a conventional blending, the domain size of the dispersed phase in continuous matrix of other polymer is of the micron scale range. While, the principle aim of nanostructure blending is to attain nanoscale dimension (less than 100 nm) of the dispersed phase. There are several approaches mentioned for preparation of nanostructure blends. The most common approaches are¹³⁻¹⁵

1. Reactive Extrusion (in situ copolymerization, graft copolymerization)
2. Block copolymerization
3. High shear processing

A graft copolymer having affinity for both polymers is normally used as compatibilizers. When the compatibilizer present above a critical concentration, they tend to reduce the domain size of dispersed phase.

The nanostructured blends mentioned in the literature are¹³⁻¹⁵

1. Poly(vinylidene fluoride) (PVDF) and polyamide 11 (PA11) Blends
2. Polypropylene (PP) and polyamide-6 (PA-6) Blend
3. Polyethylene (PE)- polyamide (PA) blends

A novel method was developed to prepare nanostructured blends (nanoblends) of polypropylene (PP) and polyamide-6 (PA-6) directly in a screw extruder. It consisted of polymerizing a monomer of PA-6, ϵ -caprolactam (ϵ -CL), in the matrix of PP. A fraction

of the latter bore 3-isopropenyl- R, R-dimethylbenzene isocyanate (TMI) which acted as growing centers to initiate PA-6 chain growth. As such, formation of PA-6 and a graft copolymer of PP and PA-6 took place simultaneously in the matrix of the PP, leading to compatibilized PP/PA-6 blends. The size of the particles of the dispersed phase (PA-6) was between 10 and 100 nm, which could not be achieved otherwise by melt blending premade PP. In practice, an interfacial emulsifier, which is often a block or graft copolymer, is added or generated in situ during blending. Its roles are to reduce the interfacial tension, help dispersion and more importantly stabilize the system by preventing particles from coalescing. Another example of reactive extrusion for fabrication of nanoscale blend is polyethylene/polyamide blend. Under normal blending these polymers are immiscible and form phase separated structure. But in the presence of graft copolymer of PE and PA, there is a formation of co-continuous blend. An in situ graft copolymer of a random copolymer ethylene-acrylate- maleic anhydride with a PA functionalized with NH_2 at one end lead to the blend compatibility. The chemistry was behind the reaction of NH_2 and anhydride.

A new mechanism of polymer modification is targeted by generating new HBP based nanoscale particle in the bioplastics matrix. The modification brings profound effect in enhancing the mechanical and rheological properties of the bioplastics¹¹.

Hyperbranched polymers (HBP) are new to materials world but offer several opportunities for bioplastic modification. They have versatile, highly branched and nanoscopic structures and thus their chemistry need to be explored to rightly fit with bioplastics in order to create nano-structures. A specific HBP, when cross-linked with anhydride, creates a nano-structure in PLA matrix. This nano-structure controlled PLA showed an improvement in the elongation of the original PLA by 9 fold¹¹. This system could be considered as a pseudo-semi-interpenetrating network system. The growing network of crosslinked HBP would cause physical interlocking with PLA chains and reduces macro-phase separation. The in-situ reactive blending of HBP and PA in PLA matrix forms a network at the PLA-HBP interface, which provided compatibility between the two phases.

These nanoscale crosslinked particles are instrumental in increasing the phenomenon of multiple crazing per unit volume, which is likely the possible energy dissipation mechanism behind the toughening of PLA bioplastic. The increase of interfacial region due to high surface area of these particles makes them effective at lower concentration. The nanoscale particle size tantamount to that of crosslinked HBP is currently not possible using conventional toughening methodologies.

HIERARCHICAL BIOCOMPOSITES FROM NANOBLEND AND NANOSTRUCTURED BIOPLASTICS

The unique physical properties and high peripheral functionalities of HBP offer many other pathways for polymer modification. HBP can play a role of novel building blocks for generating new nanostructures inside a polymer matrix ranging from core-shell to highly networked morphologies. The crosslinking of hydroxyl functional hyperbranched polyester in bioplastic matrix has demonstrated as a new method to overcome its brittleness and the modified bioplastic showed promising applications.

HBP can act as matrix modifier by creating a Stiffness-Toughness balance in biocomposites.

The hierarchical nano-biocomposites are defined as biofiber composites with nano reinforcement and modified bioplastics. The term ‘hierarchical’ relates to varying size order (nano-, micro- and macro-) of the reinforcements. This study focus to develop a new generation of multifunctional biobased composite and nanocomposites through the implementation of nano-scale, micro-scale and macro-scale reinforcements, either alone or in combination as potrayed in schematic repersentaion, Scheme 2.

Scheme 2: Various aproches to the hierarchial level reinforcements of the HBP modified bioplastic.

The objective is to generate multifunctional nano-biocomposites through varied material modifications and their combinations using appropriate nano/macro/micro-scale reinforcements to improve the performance of bioplastics. The prime function is to find special material properties at nano-scale and to integrate nano-structures to micro-, meso and macro-scale structures. The commonly available nano, micro and macro size reinforcements are nano clays, talc and natural fibers, respectively.

Nano-reinforcement of tailored HBP modified bioplastics followed by natural fiber reinforcement may provide the synergistic effects of nano- and macro- reinforcements. However, the nano-scale and macro-scale reinforcements in combination can provide superior performance.

This approach of hierarchical level reinforcements is designed in to four levels, as shown in Scheme 2.

Level I, is the nano-scale reinforcement, using nano clay, of the HBP modified bioplastic.

Level II, is the micro-scale reinforcement, using talc, of the HBP modified bioplastic.

Level III, is the usage of dual reinforcements of HBP modified bioplastic, which is further, classified in to two. Firstly, dual reinforcement of nano-sized clay and macro sized natural fiber in HBP modified bioplastic. Secondly, dual reinforcement of micro-sized talc and macro sized natural fiber in HBP modified bioplastic.

Level IV, is the combination of all the different sized reinforcement i.e, nano-clay, micro-talc and macro-natural fiber, in HBP modified bioplastic.

FUTURE DIRECTIONS

Poly lactide has shown much promise towards the building of a bioplastic regime, where it will play a pivotal role due to its affordable cost and useful property attributes. There is enormous opportunity on hand to us for tailoring the designing of HBP and study its influence on other bioplastics and their properties. HBP modified bioplastics can generate new sets of materials, which can have applications ranging from packaging to automotives. Extention of this research to higher generation hyperbranched polymers may reveal an effect on the size and molecular weight between the crosslinks of crosslinked HBP. This may be a new approach to tailor the glass transition temperature and modulus of the crosslinked HBP particles. Thus modified bioplastics can be used as a matrix for filler reinforcement such as talc and nano-clay. The functional nature of crosslinked HBP can be explored to provide the compatibility between filler and polylactide matrix

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

Amar K. Mohanty is thankful to 2009 NSERC Discovery Grant and the Premier's research chair fund for the financial support.

References:

1. Gross, R. A., Kalra, B., Biodegradable polymers for the environment. *Science*, 2002. **297**(5582): p. 803-807.
2. Carole, T. M., Pellegrino, J., Paster, M. D., Opportunities in the Industrial Biobased Products Industry. *Applied Biochemistry and Biotechnology*, 2004. **113-116**: p. 871-885.
3. Kurian, J. V., *Sorona Polymer: Present Status and Future Perspectives*. Natural Fibers, Biopolymers, and Biocomposites, ed. A.K. Mohanty, Misra, M., Drzal, L. T. 2005, Boca Raton: CRC Press.
4. Bhardwaj, R; Modification of Polylactide Bioplastic using Hyperbranched Polymer based Nanostructures, PhD Thesis, Michigan State University, MI, USA
5. Ray E. Drumright, Patrick R. Gruber, and David E. Henton, Polylactic Acid Technology. *Advance Materials*, 2000. 12(23): p. 1841-1846.
6. Goksungur, Y., Guvenc, U., Batch and continuous production of lactic acid from beet molasses by *Lactobacillus delbrueckii* IFO 3202. *Journal of Chemical Technology and Biotechnology*, 1997. 69(4): p. 399-404.
7. Timbuntam, W., Sriroth, K., Tokiwa, Y., Lactic acid production from sugar-cane juice by a newly isolated *Lactobacillus* sp. *Biotechnology Letters*, 2006. 28(11): p. 811-814.
8. Shen, X. L., Xia, L. M., Lactic acid production from cellulosic waste by immobilized cells of *Lactobacillus delbrueckii*. *World Journal of Microbiology & Biotechnology*, 2006. 22(11): p. 1109-1114.
9. Fukushima, K., Sogo, K., Miura, S., Kimura, Y., Production of D-lactic acid by bacterial fermentation of rice starch. *Macromolecular Bioscience*, 2004. 4(11): p. 1021-1027.
10. Bhardwaj, R; Mohanty, A. K; *Journal of Biobased Materials and Bioenergy*, 2007, 1(2), 191.
11. Bhardwaj, R; Mohanty, A. K. 2007. Modification of Brittle Polylactide (PLA) by Novel Hyperbranched Polymer based Nanostructures. *Biomacromolecules* 8(8): 2476-2484.
12. Mohanty and Bhardwaj; US and World Patents Pending; US 20060247387 A1 and & WO 2006119020 A2.
13. Hu, G. H., Cartier, H., Reactive Extrusion: Toward Nanoblends. *Macromolecules*, 1999. **32**: p. 4713-4718.
14. Ruzette, A. V., Leibler, L., Block copolymers in tomorrow's plastics. *Nature Materials*, 2005. **4**.
15. Shimizu, H., Li, Y., Kaito, A., and Sano, H., Formation of Nanostructured PVDF/PA11 Blends Using High-Shear Processing. *Macromolecules*, 2005. **38**: p. 7880-7883.